

PECULIARITIES OF DRAMATIC AND ROMANTIC IRONY

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This article gives detailed information about dramatic and romantic irony with the help of some examples. At the same time, it gives theoretical data of irony and its types. And the work determines several features of irony in different fields especially in aesthetics and stylistics.

The ability of identifying sarcasm and irony has got a lot of attention recently. There are several definitions given for irony. Cicero defined irony as a figure of speech in which what is stated is not what is meant. The user of irony assumes that his reader or listener understands the concealed meaning of his statement. Perhaps the simplest form of irony is rhetorical irony, when, for effect, a speaker says the direct opposite of what she means.¹

Irony can be used in a number of contexts. Irony used in drama and romantic works has some features which show and increase impressiveness of the work and according to the context and type of work, they can be called romantic and dramatic irony.

Irony in Russian literature and criticism has taken various forms: the "avenger" and "comforter" in A.I. Herzen, for example, and "mocking criticism" in the revolutionary democrats V.G. Belinskii, N.A. Nekrasov, and M.E. Saltykov-Shchedrin. Combined with humor in N.V. Gogol, irony turns into sarcasm in F.M. Dostoevsky, is parodic in Koz'ma Prutkov, and becomes romantic in A.A. Blok.

Thus, in Shakespeare's Julius Caesar, when Mark Antony refers in his funeral oration to Brutus and his fellow assassins as "honorable men" he is really saying that they are totally dishonorable and not to be trusted. Dramatic irony occurs in a play when the audience knows facts of which the characters in the play are ignorant. The most sustained example of dramatic irony is undoubtedly Sophocles' Oedipus Rex, in which Oedipus searches to find the murderer of the former king of Thebes, only to discover that it is himself, a fact the audience has known all along.

In stylistics, a statement with a double meaning that expresses mockery or cunning. In irony a word or utterance acquires in the context of speech a significance that is opposite to its literal meaning, negates it, or casts doubt up on it.

The servant of influential masters,

With what noble valor

You in inveigh with free speech against

All those whose mouths have been stopped.²

Irony is abuse and contradiction under the mask of approval and agreement. A phenomenon is deliberately characterized by a trait that it does not have, but that should have been expected. "Sometimes, pretending, one talks of what should be as if it actually existed: this is irony". Irony is "a cunning dissembling, when a man acts like a simpleton who does not know what he

¹ Dugan J. Cicero's rhetorical theory. London. 2013. p.25

² Tiutchev F.I. Ty ne rodilsya polyakom... Saint Petersburg 1940. p.30

actually does know". Irony is usually considered a type of trope, more rarely a stylistic figure of speech.

The hint at dissimulation, the "key" to irony, is not usually contained in the expression itself, but in the context or intonation, and sometimes only in the situation of the utterance. Irony is one of the most important stylistic means used in humor, satire, and the grotesque. When ironic mockery becomes a malicious, biting taunt, it is called sarcasm.

In aesthetics, irony is a kind of comic, ideological emotional evaluation, whose elementary model, or prototype, is the structural expressive principle of verbal stylistic irony. The ironic attitude presupposes superiority, or condescension, and skepticism, or mockery, which, purposely hidden, still determine the style of an artistic or publicistic work or the organization of the imagery, characterization, or plotline. The concealed character of the mockery and the mask of "seriousness" distinguish irony from humor and especially from satire.

The meaning of irony as an aesthetic category varied significantly in different periods. For example, "Socratic irony" was characteristic of antiquity; it simultaneously expressed the philosophical principle of doubt and the means of revealing the truth. Socrates pretended to hold the same views as his opponent, agreed with what he said, and imperceptibly led him to absurdity, there by revealing the narrowness of those truths that seem to be obvious to commonsense. The theory of the classical theater's so-called tragic irony has been fully developed in the modern period. The hero is self-confident and does not know that it is his own actions that are leading to his ruin. Such "irony of fate" is quite frequently called "objective irony" and, when applied to real life, the "irony of history".

Irony was given an explicit theoretical foundation and varied artistic realization during the romantic period. Romantic irony stressed the relativity of all aspects of life that are restrictive in their meaning and significance. The stagnation of everyday life, class narrow-mindedness and the foolishness of self-contained crafts and professions are depicted as something voluntary that people undertake as a joke.

Romantic irony underwent an evolution. At first it was the irony of freedom: life contained no insurmountable obstacles for its free spirits and mocked all those who tried to attribute permanent forms to life. It turned into the sarcasm of necessity: the forces of stagnation and oppression overcame life's free spirits. The poet soared high, only to be snubbed and crudely jeered at. Romantic irony exposed the discord between the dream and real life and the relativity and mutability of earthly values. At times it questioned the objective existence of these values and subordinated art to the goals of aesthetic play. Although exaggerated, Hegel's opinion of the "negative irony" of the romantics has foundation.

Irony in the conception of the Danish thinker Soren Kierkegaard is more negative and subjective in its nature and aim. He broadened it to a life principle a universal means for the subject to attain inner liberation from the necessity and bondage in which the sequential chain of life situations holds him. A number of symbolists subscribed to this view, about which A. A. Blok wrote with bitterness. For many 20th-century artists and aestheticians involved in modernism, "nihilistic" irony includes the principle of total parody and self-parody of art.

Thomas Mann developed the original concept of "epic irony" as one of the basic principles of contemporary realism. Proceeding from the universality of romantic irony, he claimed that irony is essential for epic art since it provides a view from the heights of freedom, peace, and

objectivity, unobscured by any moralizing. A specific "ironic dialectics" is reflected in Brecht's theatrical method of estrangement.

Generally, irony is contradiction under the mask of agreement. Irony carries different meaning in different fields. For example: in aesthetics, irony is a kind of comic, ideological emotional evaluation. In stylistics, a statement with a double meaning that expresses mockery or cunning. Dramatic irony occurs in a play when the audience knows facts of which the characters in the play are ignorant. Romantic irony stressed the relativity of all aspects of life that are restrictive in their meaning and significance.

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